

Design Study of Market Systems for Upcycled Plastic Woven Lifestyle Accessories in India.

Sarthak Sharad Patel & Dr. Samrat Dev

sarthak4design@gmail.com & sdev@ddn.upes.ac.in

School of Design, University of Petroleum and Energy Studies, Dehradun, Uttarakhand

Abstract

Plastic pollution is among the most pressing environmental challenges worldwide, multiplied by rising consumption of single-use packaging and polyethylene bags. Upcycled plastic weaving has emerged as an innovative craft to valorize waste plastic into lifestyle products that create environmental and social value. This study examines the market dynamics, consumer behaviour, and design preferences shaping the success of four Indian upcycled plastic weaving brands namely Recharkha, Ecokaari, Thela, and Akhirah Eco. A mixed-method research design integrated online surveys (n=150), semi-structured interviews (n=12), and content analysis of brand communication. Results show that consumers are motivated by environmental concern, aesthetic appreciation, and social impact. However, perceived high costs and limited awareness inhibit widespread adoption. The findings contribute to understanding how design-led interventions and social innovation can embed circular economy principles into daily consumption, offering pathways to scale sustainable waste management. Implications for designers, policymakers, and entrepreneurs are discussed.

Keywords: Upcycling, Circular Economy, Plastic Waste, Sustainable Design, India

1. Introduction

One of the most significant environmental problems of our day is the growth of plastic waste. More than 3.4 million tonnes of plastic are produced in India alone each year, primarily in the

form of multilayered packaging materials and thin carry bags. (CPCB, 2019). Thin polyethylene carry bags, multilayered packaging, and other single-use plastics escape formal recycling and often become visible litter or are burned, creating toxic emissions. Although Extended Producer Responsibility (EPR) laws and prohibitions have been implemented to stop the trend, their efficacy is frequently compromised by behavioural inaction and implementation issues (Gupta & Vegelin, 2016).

The circular economy, a new paradigm for sustainability is becoming more and more well-liked globally. Recycling, reuse, repair, and refurbishment are given priority in the circular economy in order to keep resource consumption and economic growth apart. (Geissdoerfer et al., 2016). Within this paradigm comes upcycling, a process in which products and materials that are no longer in use are repurposed, repaired, upgraded and remanufactured in a way that increases their value” (J. Singh, 2022). Upcycling, which is the innovative repurposing of waste materials to create goods with a higher perceived worth, presents a viable sustainable option. (Bocken et al., 2016).

Upcycling techniques have become more innovative in recent years due to the growing environmental crisis caused by plastic waste (Balu et al., 2022). Among these, the creative art of repurposed plastic weaving is a noteworthy upcycling phenomenon. Several social entrepreneurs in India have adopted ancient weaving methods to use handloom weaving to turn waste plastic into lifestyle accessories including wallets, bags, and home décor pieces. Among these, Recharkha, Ecokaari, Thela, and Akhira Eco have created unique models that integrate design innovation, livelihood creation, and environmental stewardship.

Despite the growth of the craft, limited systematic research has examined how these brands engage consumers, which factors drive purchase decisions, or how design choices affect perceptions of value. Previous studies on green consumption in India have focused on organic products and eco-labeling (Joshi & Rahman, 2015), but rarely on upcycled woven plastic goods. This research addresses this gap by exploring market dynamics and consumer perceptions across four pioneering brands.

The objectives of this study are to map the market positioning and product strategies of Recharkha, Ecokaari, Thela, and Akhira Eco and to understand consumer motivations, design preferences, and perceived barriers to adoption

2. Literature Review

Plastic pollution contributes to ecological degradation, economic loss, and health risks (Hopewell et al., 2009). The circular economy concept, defined as an industrial system that is restorative and regenerative by design (Ellen MacArthur Foundation, 2013), offers frameworks for reducing material flows and extending product lifecycles. Upcycling stands out as a valorization strategy, transforming waste into products perceived as superior in quality or purpose (Bocken et al., 2016). Prior work has demonstrated the capacity of upcycling initiatives to generate income and foster community engagement (Seelos & Mair,

2005; Hobson, 2016). The consumer acceptance and willingness to purchase upcycled products becomes essential.

Consumer adoption of environmentally responsible products is influenced by perceived benefits, social norms, and personal values (Peattie & Crane, 2005). In the Indian context, Biswas and Roy (2015) found that while environmental concern positively correlates with willingness to buy green products, price sensitivity and limited awareness are significant barriers. Joshi and Rahman (2015) similarly reported that trust in environmental claims is critical for consumer acceptance of such products.

According to Manzini (2015), design techniques can be effective instruments for transforming the social and environmental spheres. Craft-based design enhances the perceived worth of otherwise discarded materials, generates respectable employment, and makes use of local expertise when integrated into community businesses (George, 2019). Research on market acceptance is still lacking, but upcycled plastic weaving in particular has shown promise for scaling such benefits.

By incorporating a strong empirical technique to investigate how consumers interact with upcycled woven plastic products and how brands position themselves in a competitive sustainable market landscape, this study expands on existing lines of research through a framework.

Findings from earlier studies on social enterprise, design innovation, and sustainable consumerism are combined in the conceptual framework shown in Figure 1. It places environmental concern at the forefront of adoption, which is in line with research that indicates ecological awareness is a strong predictor of green purchasing behaviour (Joshi & Rahman, 2015; Biswas & Roy, 2015). The relevance of open narratives and community involvement in fostering customer trust is reflected in the mediating effects of social impact and storytelling (Peattie & Crane, 2005; Manzini, 2015). Simultaneously, functional and durable qualities as well as aesthetic appeal support the notion that design features and perceived product quality are important for creating desirability and maintaining use over time (Rex & Baumann, 2007; Bocken et al., 2016). These elements operate together to influence brand affinity, buying intention, and readiness to pay, supporting frameworks that highlight integrated value propositions as crucial for expanding circular economy practices (Kirchherr et al., 2018; Hobson, 2016). In promoting the use of upcycled plastic weaved lifestyle items, this model emphasises the interaction of social narratives, product features, and environmental motives.

Figure 1. Conceptual framework illustrating how the adoption of upcycled woven plastic items is influenced by perceptions of affordability, social effect awareness, perceived product quality, and environmental concern.

3. Methodology

This study used a convergent mixed-method approach that combined content analysis with semi-structured interviews and questionnaire surveys. (Singh and Pandey, 2018) used survey data and case analysis to examine the adoption of green products. This served as the model for the study.

3.1 Sample and Data Collection

The study targeted consumers with awareness of or experience purchasing from Rechalkha, Ecokaari, Thela, or Akhirah Eco. A purposive sampling strategy recruited 150 survey respondents via brand mailing lists and social media outreach. In addition, 12 semi-structured interviews were conducted with consumers, designers, and brand founders.

Survey questions covered demographics, brand awareness, motivations, purchase frequency, design preferences, and perceived barriers. Interviews explored deeper insights into perceived value, trust, and expectations. Content analysis included systematic review of websites, Instagram posts, and product descriptions.

3.2 Data Analysis

Survey data were analysed using descriptive statistics and cross-tabulations in Excel. Interviews were transcribed and coded thematically (Braun & Clarke, 2006). Content analysis data were categorized by narrative themes, imagery, and brand positioning.

Table 1. Demographics of Survey Respondents (n=150)

Variable	Percent age (%)
Gender (Female)	65
Age (25-40)	58
Urban Residence	70
Postgraduate Education	62
Previous Purchase	54

4. Results

The findings are presented in three parts: survey data, interview themes, and content analysis.

4.1 Survey Insights

Among respondents (n=150), 54% had purchased at least one upcycled plastic woven product. Environmental concern emerged as the strongest driver of purchase intent, reported by 82% of buyers. Social impact motivation, including livelihood support for artisans, was cited by 68%. Aesthetic appreciation (e.g., colors and patterns) motivated 56%. However, price sensitivity was high—47% reported that perceived high-cost limited repeat purchases.

When asked about preferred product categories, bags and wallets were the most popular (72%), followed by home decor (22%) and fashion accessories (6%). Respondents rated product durability and finish positively (average score: 4.2/5), but many expressed a need for more contemporary styles.

Table 2. Key Purchase Motivations

Motivation	% Reporting High Importance
Environmental Concern	82
Artisan Livelihood Support	68
Unique Aesthetics	56
Brand Storytelling	49
Price Competitiveness	42

4.2 Interview Themes

Table 3. Thematic Code Table

Theme	Code	Definition	Example Quote
Trust and Authenticity	Credible Environmental Claims	References to the need for verified sustainability information and claims.	“I only buy if I’m sure the plastic is actually recycled.”
	Transparency in Processes	Desire for clear, open communication about sourcing and production.	“They show videos of how they collect and weave the plastic, which makes me trust them.”
	Visual Documentation Builds Trust	Mention of photos, videos, or social media as proof of authenticity.	“The Instagram stories showing artisans at work are very convincing.”
Design and Identity	Craft Heritage Aesthetics	Appreciation for ethnic or traditional design elements.	“I love that these bags look ethnic...”
	Modern Functionality	Value placed on products being suited to contemporary lifestyles.	“...but still go with my work outfits.”
Barriers to Adoption	Price Sensitivity	Mention of high price as a barrier to purchase or repeat purchase.	“I want to buy more, but the price makes it an occasional splurge...”
	Comparison to Mass-Produced Alternatives	Reference to cheaper alternatives or lack of affordability.	“...especially compared to regular bags I can buy in the market.”
Emotional Connection	Support for Artisans	Feeling of satisfaction from supporting livelihoods and communities.	“It feels good to know my purchase helps women earn a living.”
	Contribution to Waste Reduction	Emotional gratification linked to reducing plastic pollution.	“I feel like I’m doing my part to keep plastic out of landfills.”

Thematic analysis of interviews yielded four main themes:

Trust and Authenticity: Buyers emphasized the importance of credible environmental claims and transparent processes. Many cited visual evidence on Instagram as building trust.

Design and Identity: Participants valued designs that blended craft heritage with modern functionality. A young professional noted: *“I love that these bags look ethnic but still go with my work outfits.”*

Barriers to Adoption: Price was consistently mentioned as a barrier, especially compared to mass-produced alternatives. One respondent shared: *“I want to buy more, but the price makes it an occasional splurge, not a regular purchase.”*

Emotional Connection: Many buyers felt an emotional bond knowing their purchase supported artisans and reduced waste.

4.3 Content Analysis

A cross-brand comparison of websites and social media revealed similar storytelling strategies. All four brands emphasized: Visual narratives of artisans weaving plastic, Impact metrics (e.g., kg of plastic saved) and Artisan empowerment messaging.

5. Discussion

The findings of this study illustrate that upcycled plastic woven products occupy a unique space at the intersection of environmental stewardship, social innovation, and design aesthetics. This combination creates a multidimensional value proposition that resonates with consumers but also introduces specific challenges for scalability and mainstream adoption.

5.1. Alignment with Circular Economy Frameworks

The strong role of environmental concern as a purchase motivator aligns with the principles of the circular economy, which emphasize reducing waste and revalorizing materials through creative processes (Ellen MacArthur Foundation, 2013). By transforming discarded plastic packaging—particularly low-value polyethene bags and multilayered wrappers—into durable products, these brands demonstrate how design can operationalize waste management in everyday consumption. This is consistent with Bocken et al. (2016), who argue that circular business models succeed when they reframe waste as a resource embedded with cultural and economic meaning.

Moreover, the narratives of transformation and impact used by Recharkha, Ecokaari, Thela, and Akhirah Eco echo Kirchherr et al.'s (2018) finding that in order to gain consumers' legitimacy and trust, successful circular economy projects need compelling narratives and unambiguous explanations of the environmental advantages.

5.2. The Role of Emotional and Social Value

The emotional bond customers expressed while buying repurposed plastic woven goods was one particularly striking revelation. The feeling of helping women's economic empowerment and artisan livelihoods was mentioned numerous times. This bolsters Manzini's (2015) view that design methods that foster community narratives and a sense of shared purpose are conducive to social innovation.

Perceived value was also impacted by emotional involvement. Customers were prepared to spend more for goods that were seen as genuine and purpose driven. This dynamic is reminiscent of (Seelos and Mair's, 2005) research on social companies, which highlights how combining environmental and social advantages can create unique market positions that are challenging for traditional rivals to copy.

5.3. Aesthetic and Functional Considerations

Design has been shown to have a significant impact on customer satisfaction and intentions to make more purchases. Many respondents said they wanted more modern designs and a wider range of colour schemes to include the products into a variety of personal and professional contexts, even if they valued the ethnic and handmade feel. This discovery is in line with (Rex and Baumann, 2007) contention that when consumers are making decisions, aesthetics and functional factors frequently take precedence over strictly ecological factors.

Brands who were able to successfully combine traditional weaving methods with contemporary or minimalist design elements appeared to pique consumers' attention more. This implies a chance for designers to collaborate with craftspeople to produce new collections that satisfy changing urban preferences while maintaining the cultural authenticity that sets these goods apart from mass-market substitutes.

5.4. Barriers to Mainstream Adoption

Although there was a lot of interest in the effects on the environment and society, perceived high prices continued to be a major obstacle. According to about 47% of study participants, pricing restricted how frequently they made purchases. This conflict is in line with (Biswas and Roy, 2015) finding that Indian consumers, especially those in the growing middle class, frequently strike a compromise between environmental concerns and financial restraints.

Upcycling in a craft setting is more labour-intensive and expensive to produce than industrial recycling. Furthermore, economies of scale are restricted by the artisanal nature of these goods. As a result, even highly motivated customers could limit their purchases to one-time indulgences rather than regular usage.

This research highlights a significant obstacle: whereas upcycled woven plastic products might establish themselves as desirable substitutes for throwaway plastic items, expanding their influence necessitates developing innovative business models that increase affordability without jeopardising the livelihoods of artisans.

5.5. Implications for Design and Branding

The study identifies a number of ways that social entrepreneurs and designers might promote the broad use of these products. Modular Product Lines: Maintaining higher-margin premium lines while lowering the price barrier for new clients may be achieved by introducing entry-level items or smaller accessories. Retail Partnerships & Co-Branding: Working with well-known stores could lower expenses and increase distribution. Lifecycle Storytelling: Sharing

the entire material's journey, from waste collection to weaving to the finished product, helps strengthen emotional connections and authentic perspectives. To ensure relevance across markets, the brands may think about creating design toolkits that assist artisans in working with urban designers to prototype and iterate new styles.

5.6. Policy and Ecosystem-Level Considerations

Upcycled plastic woven items have the ability to support livelihood creation and trash diversion, which is in line with larger policy goals like India's Swachh Bharat Mission and the new EPR frameworks. Nonetheless, the following supportive elements may be considered for a greater uptake of woven products made from recycled plastic: Rewards and Financial Assistance: Subsidies or tax breaks could assist defray increased production costs and lower the cost of goods. Labelling and Certification: Similar to current Fair-Trade or organic certifications, standards certifying recycled and upcycled products can increase consumer trust. Awareness Campaigns: Public awareness campaigns emphasising the advantages upcycled items have for the environment and society could fill in knowledge gaps and normalise buying habits. A system where small businesses are not primarily in charge of educating customers and covering the expenses of raising awareness might be established by such governmental initiatives.

6. Conclusion

This study demonstrates that upcycled plastic woven lifestyle products have strong potential to function as a waste valorization tool while generating social impact through dignified employment. The success of Rechalkha, Ecokaari, Thela, and Akhirah Eco shows that design-led enterprises can reposition plastic waste as aspirational products.

By empirically showing how environmental concern, aesthetics, and social narratives interact in customer judgements about upcycled products, the findings add to the expanding body of research on sustainable design and social entrepreneurship. They also build on earlier research by (Manzini ,2015) and (Bocken et al., 2016), emphasising the real world difficulties of striking a balance between price and handmade authenticity. This study emphasises for practitioners the need for integrative techniques for successful upcycling firms, including transparent operations, good storytelling, iterative design, and collaborations that broaden market reach.

However, to scale impact, affordability and broader market integration must be addressed. Designers should experiment with modular product ranges and contemporary aesthetics. Policymakers can support scaling through incentives, certifications, and awareness campaigns. Future research should explore lifecycle assessments of upcycled plastic products and longitudinal studies on behaviour change. Additionally, comparative studies with other upcycling models will enrich the discourse on circular design.

References

- Biswas, A., & Roy, M. (2015). Green products: An exploratory study on the consumer behaviour in emerging economies. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 87, 463–468. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2014.09.075>
- Bocken, N. M. P., de Pauw, I., Bakker, C., & van der Grinten, B. (2016). Product design and business model strategies for a circular economy. *Journal of Industrial and Production Engineering*, 33(5), 308–320. <https://doi.org/10.1080/21681015.2016.1172124>
- Braun, V., & Clarke, V. (2006). Using thematic analysis in psychology. *Qualitative Research in Psychology*, 3(2), 77–101. <https://doi.org/10.1191/1478088706qp063oa>
- Ellen MacArthur Foundation. (2013). *Towards the circular economy*. Ellen MacArthur Foundation.
- George, A. (2019). The craft of plastic: Upcycling in India. *Environment and Urbanization Asia*, 10(2), 220–236. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0975425319853300>
- Gupta, A., & Vegelin, C. (2016). Sustainable development goals and inclusive development. *International Environmental Agreements: Politics, Law and Economics*, 16(3), 433–448. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10784-016-9323-z>
- Hobson, K. (2016). Closing the loop or squaring the circle? Locating generative spaces for the circular economy. *Progress in Human Geography*, 40(1), 88–104. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0309132514566342>
- Joshi, Y., & Rahman, Z. (2015). Factors affecting green purchase behaviour. *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*, 22, 185–194. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jretconser.2014.10.003>
- Joshi, Y., & Rahman, Z. (2015). Factors affecting green purchase behaviour and future research directions. *International Strategic Management Review*, 3(1–2), 128–143. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ism.2015.04.001>
- Kirchherr, J., Reike, D., & Hekkert, M. (2018). Conceptualizing the circular economy: An analysis of 114 definitions. *Resources, Conservation and Recycling*, 127, 221–232. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.resconrec.2017.09.005>
- Manzini, E. (2015). *Design, when everybody designs: An introduction to design for social innovation*. MIT Press.
- Peattie, K., & Crane, A. (2005). Green marketing. *Journal of Business Research*, 56(3), 357–370. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0148-2963\(03\)00645-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0148-2963(03)00645-1)

Peattie, K., & Crane, A. (2005). Green marketing: Legend, myth, farce or prophesy? *Qualitative Market Research: An International Journal*, 8(4), 357–370. <https://doi.org/10.1108/13522750510619733>

Rex, E., & Baumann, H. (2007). Beyond ecolabels: What green marketing can learn from conventional marketing. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 15(6), 567–576. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2006.05.013>

Seelos, C., & Mair, J. (2005). Social entrepreneurship: Creating new business models to serve the poor. *Business Horizons*, 48(3), 241–246. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bushor.2004.11.006>

Singh, A., & Pandey, N. (2018). Green marketing and sustainable consumption: A bibliometric analysis of the existing literature. *Management of Environmental Quality*, 29(4), 761–776. <https://doi.org/10.1108/MEQ-03-2018-0053>

Singh, J. (2022). The sustainability potential of upcycling: A review. *Sustainability*, 14(10), 5989. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su14105989>